

VIII. *On the Annelida of the 'Porcupine' Expeditions of 1869 and 1870.*

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[PLATES LXXI.-LXXIII.]

Read May 19th, 1874.

Part I.—EUPHROSYNIDÆ, AMPHINOMIDÆ, APHRODITIDÆ, POLYNOIDÆ, ACOËTIDÆ,
and SIGALIONIDÆ.

THE materials from which the following observations have been made were kindly placed in my hands by the distinguished naturalists who superintended the dredging-operations in these expeditions, viz. Dr. Carpenter, Dr. Gwyn Jeffreys, and Prof. Wyville Thomson. I have, in the first place, to record my obligations to these gentlemen for their great courtesy.

EUPHROSYNIDÆ.

Of the Euphrosynidæ a minute example (*Euphrosyne lanceolata*, n. s.), about one tenth of an inch in length was dredged in 173 fathoms in sandy mud and corals off Ireland in 1869. It is at once distinguished from the common *E. foliosa* by the shape of the branchiæ, which for the most part are divided dichotomously, and terminate in lanceolate processes (Pl. LXXI. fig. 1). As in allied forms, the inferior bristles are simple; the dorsal are almost all injured in the single example, only one or two with the curved and serrated fork being visible. From *E. borealis*, CErst., another British species, it is likewise separated by the form of the branchiæ and the structure of the bristles. The late Prof. M. Sars describes¹ the branchiæ of his *E. armadillo* as having the apices "conico-acuminatis," else I should have been inclined to unite the present form therewith.

AMPHINOMIDÆ.

CHLOËIA FUCATA, De Quatref.?, occurred in considerable abundance in the collection made by Dr. Carpenter in 1870; viz. in 40 fathoms off Algiers, 60-100 fathoms east of Cape de Gatte (six miles from shore), 45 fathoms eight miles N.W. of Cape Sagres, 92 fathoms in sandy mud on Adventure Bank, 128 fathoms off Tangiers, and 227 fathoms off Cadiz—the bottom temperatures in the two latter being 55°. The species seems to be most closely connected with the *C. fucata* of M. de Quatrefages² from Mascate. It differs, however, in the presence of four very distinct eyes—a larger pair in front on each side, and a smaller pair behind.

¹ Forhandl. Vid.-Selsk. 1861, p. 55.² Annelés, ii. p. 390.

The body is somewhat elongated for a typical example of the group. Most of the specimens retain traces of colour, the dorsal cirrus being brownish purple; and some have a brownish median line on the dorsum, and a band of the same hue at the anterior part of each segment. The dorsal edge of the caruncle is likewise deep purplish.

The caruncle extends to the posterior border of the fourth segment. The tentacle is much longer than the antennæ; and the latter, again, are longer than the buccal processes (tentacles of *M. de Quatrefages*). The branchiæ are bipinnate, commence at the 4th body-segment, and terminate on the last. The tail has two blunt styles.

The dorsal fascicle springs to the exterior of the branchiæ in each foot, and consists of a brittle series of radiating bristles (Pl. LXXI. fig. 2) with serrated tips. The dorsal cirrus takes its origin from the same papilla. The ventral division is furnished with a fan-shaped tuft of bristles, which are more slender and elongated in the centre of the bundle. The bifid tips of the bristles diminish from above downward. The upper series (Pl. LXXI. fig. 3) have a large process beyond the fork, while the lower (fig. 4) have a shorter. The ventral cirrus is pale in the preparations, and comes from the posterior and inferior edge of the bristle-papilla. It is about the same length as the dorsal; and both continue to the last segment. Air readily passes into the central cavity of the dorsal bristles; and, in common with the others, they have a minutely granular appearance under the microscope. Acetic acid demonstrates a considerable amount of calcareous matter in their composition, a flexible translucent chitine remaining, while the dorsal bristles lose their serrations. Some of the bristles show fine transverse lines, which even notch the edge—a feature more conspicuous after the addition of the acid.

APHRODITIDÆ.

The representatives of the Aphroditidæ are three, viz.:—*Aphrodita aculeata*, L., young examples of which occurred in 690 and 257 fathoms on Stations Nos. 3 & 8 on the Channel slope in 1870, and in 90 fathoms off the west coast of Ireland in 1869; *Lætmonice filicornis*, Kbg., off Rockall in 164 fathoms, and in 358 fathoms on the Channel slope; and *Hermione hystrix*, Sav., in 40–80 fathoms off Algiers in 1870.

POLYNOIDÆ.

Lepidonotus squamatus, L., was dredged in 30–40 fathoms on stony and muddy ground off Dingle Bay, Ireland, in 1869, and *Eunoa nodosa*, Sars, in 690 fathoms on the Channel slope in 1870.

EUNOA HISPANICA, n. s. Dredged in 539 fathoms in the Atlantic (Channel slope) 1870. The single specimen is fragmentary and without scales. There is a pale purplish hue along the dorsal and ventral surfaces. The eyes are remarkably large; indeed the pairs almost touch each other; and, from the whitish centre in the spirit-preparation, each appears to have a lens—a feature, however, probably due to the opacity of the translucent covering. The palpi are smooth. The inferior cirrus is long, slender, and smooth,

reaching even beyond the tips of the bristles. The latter are yellowish, not very numerous in either branch, and characteristic. The dorsal division bears tolerably straight bristles, with an unusually prolonged smooth tip (Pl. LXXI. fig. 5, and again more highly magnified in fig. 6). The ventral series (Pl. LXXI. fig. 7) have also a very long smooth termination, and a comparatively short region with spines. The bristle represented has intermediate or average characters. This form comes nearest the *Eunoa scabra*, Örst. (*E. ørstedii*, Mgrn.), but it differs in the more pointed anterior lobes of the head, the much larger size of the eyes (which are considerable in *E. ørstedii*), in the smoothness of the cirri and palpi, in the greater length of the ventral cirri, and, lastly, in the characteristic structure of the bristles, which have a much longer smooth portion at the tip. A single loose scale with a series of minute, pointed papillæ in the usual positions, a few large conical processes, and a few cilia occurred in the bottle; but its ownership is of course open to question. It is much softer and smoother than that of *E. ørstedii* or *E. nodosa*.

LAGISCA JEFFREYSI, n. s. Dredged in the Expedition of 1869 in the tube of a *Eunice* in 163 fathoms off the west coast of Ireland, and also in a free condition on the same ground (muddy sand), and in 690 fathoms on the Channel slope in 1870. It is an interesting species, which in superficial characters somewhat resembles *Harmothoë imbricata*, so that there is some excuse for collectors mistaking it. The same may be said of *L. rarispina*, Sars, which Dr. Malmgren saw in the bottles containing *H. imbricata* in the British Museum. It may be recognized externally by its more slender bristles (both dorsal and ventral), and the greater delicacy and (under a lens) minutely spinous nature of the scales, as well as the longer and more tapering dorsal cirri. There are 45 segments bearing bristles; and the tail is not quite complete.

The head of this form somewhat resembles that of *Harmothoë imbricata*; but the eyes are decidedly larger. The tentacle is longer and less dilated below the tip; indeed the specimens scarcely show any dilatation. The antennæ are shorter; but the palpi are similar, having minute papillæ. The tentacular cirri and tentacle are covered with very long papillæ, with a slight dilatation at the tip, and thus contrast with those of *Harmothoë imbricata*, irrespective of the presence of the enlargement in the latter below the termination.

The scales appear to reach the number of 14 pairs. They are rounded in front, somewhat reniform posteriorly, and throughout (in the spirit-preparations) of a uniform greyish hue. Their surface is nearly smooth to the naked eye; but under a lens the whole is densely covered by a series of minute, pointed, slightly brownish spines, and the free portion is profusely ciliated (Pl. LXXI. fig. 8). The cilia are pellucid tapering structures, terminating in a slightly dilated tip. A considerable part of the body posteriorly is devoid of scales. The dorsal cirri extend beyond the tip of the bristles, and are covered with long cilia similar to those on the scales. In both organs these are

much longer and more numerous than in *L. rarispina*. The ventral cirri have a few short cilia, and extend nearly to the tip of the fleshy portion of the foot.

The dorsal division of the foot has somewhat stout bristles (Pl. LXXI. fig. 9), and the tip has a tendency to follow the same form as in the ventral. This is observed in a more highly magnified view in fig. 10, while another with a sharper tip is seen in Pl. LXXIII. fig. 17, and a third in Pl. LXXIII. fig. 18, sketched from one of the shorter (developing?) forms toward the body-line of the dorsum, and having a slender process at the tip. The ventral division commences superiorly with a series having very long tips, the rows of spines being much finer and more dense than in *Harmothoë imbricata*—indeed, in this respect approaching *Dasylepis asperrima*. The peculiar shape of the terminal portion is distinctive (Pl. LXXI. fig. 11, representing one of the longer, not longest, forms). Some of those next the upper series also show a distinct process beneath the tip (Pl. LXXI. fig. 12). The tips diminish in length in the usual manner toward the ventral surface, those at the lower edge showing no secondary process.

Malmgren's descriptions and figures demonstrate considerable differences between his forms (*L. rarispina* and *L. propinqua*) and the present. It is a fact of interest also in connexion with the strictness necessary in all scientific drawings, that his artist has overlooked the fundamental condition of such bristles, viz. to have alternate rows of minute spines or spinous processes. None of the specimens exhibited the elongated processes on the scales shown by Malmgren in *L. rarispina*, and, in some, few or none of the bristles of the inferior branch showed the secondary process beneath the tip—characters which diverge both from the latter and *L. propinqua*.

HARMOTHOË IMBRICATA, L., occurred in 60–160 fathoms six miles E. of Cape de Gatte. In a specimen of *Harmothoë floccosa*, Sav., dredged off the west coast of Ireland in 173 fathoms, some of the posterior ventral cirri had a few clavate papillæ. *Harmothoë anti-lopes*, M'Intosh, is not uncommon in both collections, being found with the latter in (No. 6) 358 and (No. 11) 567 fathoms on the Channel slope, in the Atlantic, and outside Gibraltar in 227 fathoms.

EVARNE IMPAR, Johnst. An example from 567 fathoms (Station No. 1, 1870) does not show the large tubercles on the scales, and the cilia along the border of the latter are unusually long. The characters in some respects (except the slenderness of the ventral bristles) approach certain varieties of *Harmothoë imbricata*. The scales, moreover, have none of the ordinary brown touches, being pale greyish. The same variety was procured in Station No. 6 (358 fathoms), and outside Gibraltar.

EVARNE JOHNSTONI¹, n. s. Dredged at Station 3, 1870, in 690 fathoms in the Atlantic.

¹ In honour of the late Dr. George Johnston, of Berwick-on-Tweed, who did much to bring the Annelida into notice in this country.

The species is roughly distinguished from *E. impar* by the deep brownish hue of the dorsum, by the minute and rather indistinct eyes and the brownish purple proboscis, by the structure of the tips of the ventral bristles and their greater delicacy, and by the longer and more delicate dorsal bristles, which give the observer quite a different impression, though somewhat difficult to describe in words.

The head has the same form as in *E. impar*, and is pale throughout, no pigment occurring at the base of the tentacle. The eyes appear only as minute black points; two lie at the posterior border of the head, almost hidden by the collar; two (of the same minute size) are situated to the front and outside these, as in the ordinary species. The tentacle is absent; antennæ pale and filiform; palpi pale with filiform tips; tentacular cirri absent. A single reniform scale occurred in the vessel. It had long clavate papillæ on the usual surface and border, thinly distributed. The dorsal cirrus has a filiform tip without enlargement, and rather long clavate papillæ, sparsely distributed. The ventral cirrus has also a filiform tip, slightly enlarged (probably from the spirit) at the end, and with short clavate papillæ. It reaches considerably beyond the base of the lowest bristles.

The dorsal branch of the foot bears bristles of a similar character to those of *E. impar*, but they are on the whole longer and more slender, with better-marked spinous rows. The smooth portion at the tip, again, is decidedly shorter than in the common species. The tip, moreover, shows a characteristic conformation in some cases, having a slight mucro at the termination, then a shallow notch, and another elevation or faint mucro a little above the first row of spikes. One of the stronger bristles is represented in Pl. LXXI. fig. 13. A long clear shaft projects beyond the fleshy part of the foot before the rows of spikes appear; so that the bristles are comparatively long. The tendency to differentiation of the tip is observed in fig. 14 (from another strong bristle). The superior edge of the ventral series has a few with tips so attenuate that it is difficult to make out their structure; the bifid condition, however, appears to be present. The next lower series have much longer and stronger tips; and though the extremity is extremely delicate and translucent, the bifid condition is apparent. The terminal hook is short, and very slightly curved; and the secondary process is rather short and broad, and passes far up. The rows of spines are distant and well marked. The tips of the succeeding (lower) bristles become broader and shorter; but the character of the termination remains the same. All are very translucent and delicate. Toward the inferior edge the tip is simple, only a faintly developed hook being present. One of the elongated forms near the dorsal edge of the fascicle is shown in Pl. LXXI. fig. 15. The arrangement of the spines and the short bifid tip are characteristic. Fig. 16 represents a bristle from the middle of the foot; it is exceedingly translucent and very faintly serrated. A more highly magnified tip, corresponding to each kind, is given in fig. 17 (corresponding to fig. 15) and in fig. 18 (corresponding to fig. 16).

It is curious that in both examples of the species the proboscis is extruded. From

an examination of many preparations of *E. impar* this would not seem to occur frequently; and it is possible the same cause acts here as in the case of the deep-sea fishes, which are drawn up with eyes and intestine projecting.

HERMADION ASSIMILE, M'L., was dredged in 160 fathoms east of Cape de Gatte (six miles from shore) in 1870.

ANTINOË FINMARCHICA, Mgrn. In his 'Annulata Polychæta' Dr. Malmgren mentions¹ (in two lines) a species of this name having thirty-five segments, the elytra scarcely if at all ciliated, and stouter and shorter bristles than in *A. sarsi*. A small translucent specimen which was dredged off the west coast of Ireland (Donegal) in 20 and 420 fathoms, in the Expedition of 1869, seems to agree with all that is published about the above-mentioned species.

On contrasting it with *A. sarsi* of the same size, the head is found to be similar; but the eyes seem slightly larger. The slender cirri with filiform tips are furnished with long and conspicuous clavate papillæ, the latter often showing a fine terminal ciliary process. The soft pellucid scales have short and sparsely distributed clavate papillæ along the outer and posterior borders; but the general surface has only a few sparse subacute papillæ, occasionally with the summits curiously truncated. Most of the papillæ show the fine palpcils at the tip.

The dorsal bristles are translucent, sharply tapered from the commencement of the spinous portion to the tip, so as to give them a peculiar character. Those next the ventral series (in the ordinary position under the microscope) are nearly straight (Pl. LXXII. fig. 1), while a thicker and more curved group occupy the inner edge (Pl. LXXII. fig. 2). Contrasted with the bristles from a specimen of *A. sarsi* they are on the whole much longer, less curved, more acutely tapered at the tip, and with more closely arranged spinous rows. The ventral bristles, again, are decidedly stouter than in *A. sarsi*, and the character of the tip differs. Superiorly, instead of those with capillary tips, are bristles with a very long and delicate portion of appreciable breadth, distinctly spined, and ending in a slightly curved point. The spinous rows continue nearly to the latter. The tips gradually diminish in length toward the inferior edge, and the spinous rows are closer. Some show a tendency to have long filaments at the tip as in *A. mollis*; but the feature is indistinct.

ANTINOË MOLLIS, M. Sars. In an excellent brochure published lately by Prof. G. O. Sars², from the materials left by his distinguished father, this form is described as *Lænilla mollis*. It seems to me, however, to be linked in a very close manner to the foregoing. Two fragments were procured in 257 fathoms in the Atlantic in 1870.

¹ Page 13.

² 'Bidrag til Kundskaben om Christianiafjordens Fauna,' 1873, p. 7, pl. xiv.

The head is at once distinguished from the previous form by the large size of the eyes, both anterior and posterior. The palpi have minute papillæ. The scales are furnished with the same sparsely distributed clavate papillæ, but differ in having a close array of short acicular spines (which are much more numerous than represented by Prof. Sars) scattered over the surface. The ventral cirri have short clavate papillæ.

The dorsal bristles are slightly yellowish, and, though as conspicuous in size as those of *A. finmarchica*, are much less acutely tapered at the tip, and have closer rows of spines. The contour and curves also diverge. The superior ventral bristles have slightly shorter tips than in *A. finmarchica*; and the rows of spines are not so distinctly separated. The tip is similar, viz. slightly hooked; but the spines become so elongated toward the tip that they stand out on each side like a series of filaments (Pl. LXXII. fig. 3, and the same bristle more highly magnified in fig. 4, the specimen being from the middle of the foot).

PHYLLANTINOË MOLLIS, n. s. Dredged in 539 fathoms in the Atlantic, 1870. The fragmentary specimen measured about $\frac{3}{4}$ inch. There are about forty segments besides head and tail. The whole body is soft and delicate; and very few bristles were found in any of the feet. The dorsum has a brownish colour throughout; and the pigment posteriorly is somewhat regularly disposed in the segments. The body is characteristically elongated, and tapers much posteriorly. The head differs from most of its allies in the very large size and situation of the eyes. The posterior pair lie quite at the posterior border; the anterior, which are about twice as large as the former, occupy the lateral region of the cephalic prominence. The pairs are comparatively close to each other, and appear to have lenses. The median fissure for the tentacle is deeply marked, and almost splits the head into halves. No scales were present.

The structure of the feet could not be fully made out from the condition of the specimen; but they seem to differ considerably from the ordinary types. Anteriorly the dorsal division is much elevated in many as a soft process, probably for the attachment of the scale; while the ventral branch posteriorly projects as a long soft lobule. The dorsal bristles (Pl. LXXII. fig. 5) are short and stout, very translucent, considerably curved, and with prominent rows of spines. The specimen figured is one of the largest and least curved. There is a smooth portion at the tip. The ventral bristles (Pl. LXXII. fig. 6) are extremely slender and translucent, both as regards shaft and tip. The latter is long and tapered, and ends in a slender point, which in some is slightly bent. The spinous rows have the usual arrangement, and disappear before reaching the extremity. There is no form which appears to resemble this species.

LEPIDASTHENIA BLAINVILLII, Aud. & Ed. Dredged in 45 fathoms, eight miles off Cape Sagres, in 1870. An elongated form with distinct characters. The colours have, for the most part, disappeared; but the dorsum is still somewhat brownish along the

median line, and the outer part of the scales is tinted of a pale brownish hue. The bristle-bearing segments amount to eighty-seven; and the feet are deeply cut. The body tapers from head to tail and terminates in the anus, on each side of which there is a short cirrus. The head is small, and covered by the first pair of scales. Eyes four, somewhat indistinct; two placed near the posterior border, and two (which are wider apart than the former) in front of the prominent lateral region. Tentacle absent; but the base is of a dusky brown hue, thus causing the somewhat elevated divisions of the head next it to appear in relief. Antennæ smooth. Palpi absent. Tentacular cirri long, filiform, and smooth. There is no trace of enlargement below the tips of any of these processes. The scales are almost all detached, so that it is difficult to determine them exactly; but they appear to number about thirty pairs, the first occurring on the second segment and the last reaching the anal papilla; they are pellucid, smooth, iridescent, brownish organs, and under a high power are minutely granular, like the scales of certain fossil fishes. In the pigment-region, moreover, pentagonal or hexagonal spaces are formed with a clear point in the centre of each. A few clavate papillæ occur at intervals on the posterior surface and edge. From the surface of attachment various finely branched nerves (?) proceed to the circumference. The first pair seemed to be large; but several loose scales exceeded them, so that a regular diminution from head to tail may not hold.

Each foot, when viewed from the dorsum, is bifid, having a long pointed papilla in front, and one less acute posteriorly. The same appearance is noticed from the ventral surface, the bristles emerging between the papillæ. The dorsal cirrus arises near the base superiorly, and is a smooth tapering process extending to the tip of the bristles. The inferior cirrus springs about the middle of the foot, reaches a little beyond the angle of the fork, is filiform, tapering, and smooth. Between this and the process at the base of the foot there is a line of clavate papillæ. Viewed laterally the foot is pointed from below upward, a slight curve only existing at the dorsal edge; the tip seems to be furnished with whitish pigment along the border of the papillæ. The dorsal division is represented only by a spine, the blunt point of which projects as a prominent process covered with cutaneous tissues to the exterior of the dorsal cirrus. The ventral branch has a vertical series of dull yellowish bristles projecting between the pointed papillæ of the feet. The superior group (Pl. LXXII. fig. 7) have long tapering tips ending in a slight mucro or thickening of the point. The portion beneath is scaly rather than spinous, from a series of sheath-like processes, which, in the position of the specimen figured, are seen somewhat on their edge; they form the usual alternate double rows; and their arrangement often gives the bristle the aspect of a diminishing rod with a spiral band. The inferior series, often separated by an interval, commences with bristles having the type of the former, but with shorter tips, terminated by a slightly curved hook; and the bifid nature soon becomes developed in the others (Pl. LXXII. fig. 8). The large scale-like processes stand out prominently; but it is difficult to represent these satisfac-

torily, as every change of position alters the appearances. The tips become shorter at the ventral edge; but the terminal hook and secondary process remain.

The specimen afforded a site for a swarm of *Loxosomæ*, which occurred on the feet and dorsum beneath the scales. MM. Audouin and M.-Edwards mention that Blainville¹ figures a *Polynoë scolopendrina* which differs quite from that form in having scales extending to the posterior extremity of the body; they therefore term the form *P. blainvillii*. In all probability the *P. elegans* of Prof. Grube² refers to the same species.

LEPIDASTHENIA LONGISSIMA, Blainville. Dredged in 45 fathoms off Cape Sagres, 1870. The specimen is imperfect, consisting only of the anterior region. In external appearance it is distinguished from the preceding by the somewhat large head, the small though better-defined eyes, and the shorter bristles. The head has two tumid lobes on each side. Eyes small; the posterior pair are placed some distance in front of the posterior border; the anterior pair are further apart, and occupy the front of the lateral eminence. Tentacles and palpi absent. Tentacular cirri similar to those in *L. blainvillii*; the cephalic processes appear to be somewhat larger. The dorsum is brownish in front in the median line, the pigment being transversely barred some distance behind the head. The scales appeared to be similar to those in the former species; but all had been injured before preservation. The same sparsely distributed clavate cilia are present.

The feet are similar to those of *L. blainvillii*, having, when viewed from either surface, bifid extremities and intermediate bristles. The dorsal cirrus, however, is longer, and arises from a point nearer the extremity of the foot. The ventral cirrus is somewhat larger at the base than in the former species; and the row of clavate papillæ running from the cirrus to the inner ventral process is more distinct. The dorsal branch is represented, as in the former, only by a single spine covered by the cutaneous tissues, the whole forming a conical papilla. The ventral division of the foot has a series of bristles with simple tapering tips and scale-like rows, the spinous region being much shorter than in the former species, as observed in Pl. LXXII. fig. 9, which represents one of the superior bristles. Toward the ventral border the tips become still shorter (Pl. LXXII. fig. 10), with a slight hook at the extremity, and the spines are continued almost to the latter. When the bristle is seen from the front or the back it is shaped like a feather, since the tip is not so attenuate as in the superior series. In the figure the bristle is slightly turned round, so as to show the rapid diminution above the commencement of the spinous rows. At the ventral edge of the series a few have the shape represented in Pl. LXXII. fig. 11.

¹ Dict. des Sc. Nat. art. Vers, p. 459, pl. x. f. 2.

² Actin. Echin. u. Würmer des Adriat. u. Mittelmeers, 1840, p. 85.

Blainville's figure of *Eumolpe scolopendrina*¹ represents an elongated form with much smaller scales than the foregoing *Lepidasthenia blainvillii*; and the dorsal division of the foot (in fig. 2a, *op. cit.*) has a tuft of short hairs, and a dorsal cirrus with a dilated extremity. The ventral bristles are in two tufts—an upper small and an inferior large group. The scales proceed to the end of the body. The feet are similar in shape and longer than those of the next species. His *Eumolpe longissima*², from the shores of Genoa, is a form with a narrower and much longer body, with eighteen pairs of very small scales at the margins of the body, and with the tips of the tentacular cirri and tentacle enlarged at the extremity. The superior lobe of the foot has a tuft of fine bristles; and the dorsal cirri are enlarged near the tip. Though I would not trust much to figures alone in such a case, there are certain close resemblances and mutual relations between Blainville's and the 'Porcupine' specimens. The feet in both are similarly pointed from below upward; the bristles of the latter species (*E. longissima*) are shorter than those of the former; and the relations of the dorsal cirri, the ventral cirri, and the size of the feet are the same. Blainville's artist may have represented the forms with developing scales; and the bulbous condition of the dorsal cirri may likewise have been exaggerated. The *Polynoë malleata*, *P. tuta*, and *P. vittata*, Grube³, are species having elongated bodies with numerous scales, but they do not seem to approach the foregoing forms.

ACOËTIDÆ.

PANTHALIS ÆRSTEDI, Kinberg. In an example dredged in 477 fathoms outside the Strait of Gibraltar the second or strong series of bristles had a deep brownish or amber colour; and rows of spines occurred on the posterior edge of the bristle, where in the ordinary form none appear.

EUPANTHALIS KINBERGI, n. s. Found by Dr. Carpenter at a depth of 92 fathoms on Adventure bank in 1870.

The species is about $1\frac{1}{2}$ in. long, and somewhat resembles *Eupompe*, differing, however, from any example of the Acoëtidæ described by Kinberg in having sessile eyes. The head is rounded, as in the Polynoidæ, with two large eyes furnished with "lenses" on the lateral prominences in front, and two smaller a little behind. There is no tentacle in the specimen; but on each side of the median groove is a filiform or slightly subulate

¹ Atlas, Dict. des Sc. Nat. pl. x. f. 2 & 2a. The reference in the text (vol. lvii. p. 459) simply is, l'E. scolopendrine=*E. scolopendrina*, Sav. *loc. cit.* p. 25, no. 6, &c.

² Vers, vol. lvii. p. 459; Atlas, pl. x. f. 3 & 3a.

³ Archiv für Naturges. 1855, p. 81.

antenna. The tentacular cirri are larger than the latter, and arise from the ordinary basal process. There is a little brownish pigment on the head. The proboscis is extruded, and has the usual papillæ at the tip, besides two superior and two inferior brownish fangs and about four short blunt teeth on each side. The dorsal cirrus is a short, almost conical, process, with an enlarged base and tapering tip. The ventral is longer and more slender, but does not reach the extremity of the fleshy part of the foot. There is the usual soft process between the dorsal cirrus and the tip of the foot.

The uniramous foot bears superiorly curved subulate bristles finely serrated from base to apex, and more slender than those represented in Pl. LXXII. fig. 14 (from the ventral edge of the foot); others are more delicate, the tip beyond the enlarged base having widely distant and opposite setæ (Pl. LXXII. fig. 12, one of the smaller examples). The stout bristles (fig. 13) have a long terminal serrate whip, and the shaft at the base of the latter has a blunt hook and a brush of setæ. A tuft of bristles, similar in structure to the superior series, occurs at the ventral edge (fig. 14, and a lateral view in fig. 15); but there are none with the widely distant setæ on the terminal portion. The most remarkable feature is the entire absence of the "brush-like" bristles so characteristic of *Panthalis ærstedii*, Kbg.

Such scales as remained presented a peculiar funnel-shaped aspect, the anterior half being pale, the posterior madder-brown, deepest on the under surface. Microscopically they had a reticulated appearance, from the pentagonal or hexagonal arrangement on the posterior half; the aspect, indeed, resembled a section of cork. The surface was also studded with minute papillæ and brownish granules.

SIGALIONIDÆ.

STHENELAIS ATLANTICA, n. s. Dredged in 305 fathoms, at Station 2, 1870.

A portion of the anterior region of the body only is present. The head is furnished with four distinct eyes, observable from the dorsum and situated at the base of the tentacle, close together on each side. The scales are somewhat rounded or ovoid in front, reniform posteriorly, covered with sparsely distributed but distinct papillæ, and having throughout the greater extent of the margin a fringe of short clavate papillæ, longest exteriorly. The papillæ are decidedly longer and more slender, as well as more numerous, than in *S. zetlandica*; and palpcils occur frequently on the summit (Pl. LXXII. fig. 16).

The superior division of the foot bears finer bristles, with more delicate serrations, than in *S. zetlandica*; but the papillæ have similar dimensions. The inferior branch possesses similar papillæ with warts or secondary processes at the tip: the lobes of this division are not boldly marked. The superior ventral bristles (Pl. LXXII. fig. 17) have

about six rows of spines at the upper part of the shaft; and the terminal division has three or four segments, the basal (in the case of those possessing four) being about as long as the three distal; the tips are slender and bifid. The next lower series are stouter, with about four distinct spinous rows on the upper part of the shaft, and a terminal division of one or two segments, the tip resembling the beak of an eagle. The inferior series are slender, with about two rows of spines at the upper part of the shaft, and a terminal region of two or four divisions, with a delicately bifid tip. There appear to be some minute warts along the inferior margin of the foot. The ventral cirrus is slender and rather short, scarcely reaching the tip of the foot.

STHENELAIS LIMICOLA, Ehlers, occurred in 30–370 fathoms off the Irish coast in 1869, and an eyeless variety in 420 fathoms in the same region.

STHENELAIS JEFFREYSI, n. s. Dredged in 165 fathoms off the west coast of Ireland (Station 9) in 1869.

The specimen is about $1\frac{1}{2}$ inch long, and apparently eyeless (in spirit). The scales are furnished with a limited number of papillæ, which greatly exceed those of *S. boa* in length, though they are much less numerous. The surface of the scale is comparatively smooth; and the organs are delicate, translucent, and somewhat reniform in outline. The number of papillæ on the truncated exterior border is about ten (Pl. LXXII. fig. 18); and the contrast with those of *S. boa* is evident by glancing at a fragment of a scale from the latter similarly magnified (fig. 19). In the latter figure the edge of the scale has been doubled, so as to show (somewhat out of focus) the smaller papillæ on the surface. Very large examples of *S. boa* from Herm have the same relations between the various papillæ of the scales.

The superior division of the foot bears about three papillæ at its tip, and a series of the usual slender bristles, most delicately serrated, with fine and rather closely set rows of spines. The inferior branch has one or two papillæ at the tip of the central part, and one on each of the lobes above and below. The superior series of bristles have four rows of spines at the end of the shaft, and a most delicate tapering terminal process, finely pointed (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 1, which shows a bristle somewhat compressed by others). From the neighbourhood of the inferior lobule are some with shorter tips, and a claw with a flat secondary process filling up the concavity. There are apparently two or three segments in the terminal process of the latter bristles, a basal about half the total length (when there are two segments), and one or two shorter beyond (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 2). The most inferior are delicate bristles with a long terminal process of six or seven segments, and a very minute claw at the tip, the secondary process again filling up the hollow (fig. 3). Ventrally there are thus three series:—(1) the strong superior, with tapering filiform tips; (2) the short bifid forms; and (3) the

inferior, with long delicate bifid tips. All are very delicate and translucent, and the basal region of the terminal process is often wrinkled. The appearance of the bristles varies (as usual) with their position. The ventral cirrus extends nearly as far as the tip of the fleshy part of the foot.

EUSTHENELAIS HIBERNICA, n. s. Dredged in 106 fathoms in 1862, on Station 8, off the west coast of Ireland, and in 45 fathoms off Cape Sagres in 1870.

The form is allied to *Leanira*, but distinguished by having the inferior group of the ventral bristles bifid.

The head is eyeless in the spirit-preparations. Tentacle rather longer than the tentacular cirri, and with two minute processes at the base. Palpi of the usual elongated form, with a scoop-like sheath at the base; the peduncle of the tentacular cirrus bears four processes besides the bristles. The tentacular cirrus proper is external (dorsally), and somewhat less than the tentacle. A smaller process lies within, its filiform tip being shorter than the former. Beneath are two processes—an inner, short and somewhat blunt, with the tip extending a little beyond the peduncle, and another slender subulate process nearly half the length of the tentacular cirrus. The long slender bristles are directed forward and inward. All the scales are absent.

The dorsal lobe of the foot has long papillæ at the tip, and finely serrated bristles, of the usual character (a series more distinctly, another more minutely spinous); the inferior division carries also long papillæ, slightly diminished at the tip. The superior ventral bristles have rather slender shafts, and the distal ends are furnished with from six to nine whorls of spikes. The tips are long jointed processes ending in a capillary termination—resembling those of *Sthenelais* or *Sigalion* rather than *Leanira*, since the necklace-like canaliculi are absent (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 4, the figure representing one of those next the superior lobe of the foot); the serratures on the tip of the shaft are more numerous in this kind, but the jointed extremities are much shorter. The segmentation of the tip is faint and widely distant. The basal segment is fully one third the length of the process. In the stouter bristles below, the ends of the shafts are smooth, and the divisions of the terminal process shorter. The slender group at the ventral border have a slightly enlarged tip, obscurely bifid (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 5). The character of these bristles also leans to the two forms previously mentioned, and not to *Leanira*. A few of the inferior group of ventral bristles present one or two spines at the end of the shaft. The dorsal cirrus (branchia?) is short anteriorly, but gradually increases in length till about the middle of the body. There is a single large ciliated pad on the dorsal edge of the foot, and about three smaller pads in the curve below the cirrus. The ventral cirrus is long and subulate, reaching almost to the tip of the foot; as usual, it is longest on the first foot.

SIGALION MATHILDÆ, Aud. & Ed. A fragmentary specimen dredged in 7 to 51 fathoms (No. 50) along the shore of the Algerine coast, between Capes Falcon and Tenez, in 1870.

LEANIRA HYSTRICIS, Ehlers¹. Simultaneously with the diagnosis of this and certain other Annelids of the 'Porcupine' Expedition, published by Dr. Ehlers in the 'Annals and Magazine of Natural History' for April 1874, I had mentioned the same form (pp. 268, 269) under the title of *L. lævis*; Dr. Ehlers's name, however, may with propriety be adopted. My examples were dredged in 808 fathoms off the south-west coast of Ireland (Station 2) in 1869, on a bottom of soft thick mud. The same station is amongst those mentioned by Dr. Ehlers.

It is a comparatively small species, none measuring more than an inch in length.

The head is slightly dusky from the presence of pigment along the anterior border. The tentacle is remarkably short and small, being shaped like the handle of an awl—narrow at the base, dilated in the middle, and tapering to a blunt point at the tip. The palpi spring close together on each side inferiorly, and have throughout a perfectly smooth investment; they are long and tapering; each has at its base, towards the inner side and ventral surface, the usual scoop-shaped lamella. Immediately above the palpus on each side is a peduncle bearing three processes, viz.:—superiorly a tentacular cirrus about a fifth the length of the palpus; inferiorly a minute organ of the same nature, extending only a short way beyond the peduncle; and an awl-handle-shaped minute process attached to the base of the peduncle superiorly. The latter is similar in form to the median tentacle, near which it is placed. Inferiorly the oral aperture has prominent rugose lips, with a blunt papilla on each side of the median fissure in front. No eyes are visible in the spirit-preparations; and none showed traces of the bristles usually present in allied forms on the peduncle of the tentacular cirri. Only a single scale remained attached to a specimen. It is rounded, translucent, and perfectly smooth in outline and surface.

The first foot is directed forward, its dorsal division being represented by a superior rounded papilla, which bears about a dozen digit-like processes and a series of fine hair-like bristles (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 6), minutely or in others more distinctly and spirally spinous. The inferior lobe has characteristic spirally marked bristles with tapering extremities (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 7, one of the superior forms), those near the spine being stoutest, while of the others the superior, as usual, are stronger than the inferior. The distal margin of the shaft of these bristles has blunt projections or spines analogous to those in *Phyllodoce* and others. The inferior lobe has also a papilla superiorly and

¹ Ann. Nat. Hist. ser. 4, vol. xiii. p. 292, April 1874. The specimens examined by Dr. Ehlers were in all probability those given by Dr. Carpenter and Prof. Wyville Thomson to the lamented Prof. E. Claparède, and procured in 1869 at a greater depth than 500 fathoms.

inferiorly, each being larger than those on the dorsal lobe. The inferior cirrus is stout, and reaches nearly to the tip of the fleshy part of the foot.

The superior division of the foot gradually increases in size from before backward, until it projects about as far as the inferior; and the bristles also become stronger and longer, a few smooth hairs appearing in each bundle. The digit-like papillæ, however, diminish in number; and, as a rule, there are only two in each division of the foot in the middle of the body, those of the inferior lobe being the larger. Posteriorly the superior division has three of the papillæ above the bristle-bundle, the inferior frequently only a single large pedunculated clavate process. The ventral cirrus is also reduced in size. The inferior bristles of the ventral tuft in the same region have a more distinct enlargement at the distal end of the shaft (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 8). Anteriorly there is no branchial process; and it is only at the twenty-fourth foot that a minute one appears, which gradually elongates as we proceed backward, so as to extend outward as far as the tip of the foot.

The bristles are rather shorter and proportionally stouter than in *Leanira yhleni*; there is no ciliated pad on the dorsal edge of the foot; and the papillæ of the latter do not show the disparity in size characteristic of *Leanira yhleni*. The ventral cirrus is also shorter, and in the preparations shows no process at the base. It diverges much from *Leanira tetragona* in regard to the tentacle, bristles, and other parts.

At the anterior end of a fragmentary specimen is apparently a crustacean parasite immersed in the dorsal muscles.

LEANIRA YHLENI, Malmgren? Dredged in 81 fathoms off Cape Finisterre (Station 10), and in 45 fathoms off Cape Sagres, in 1870. It is a form of some size; but none of the specimens are complete. The largest fragment measures about 2 inches.

The head has a little dark pigment in front, on each side of the base of the tentacle. The latter is scarcely as long as the tentacular cirrus, and more slender; at its base are two short lamelliform processes. A pair of eyes of small size lie on each side of the tentacle, and a larger anterior pair in the sulcus beneath. Two elongated tapering palpi spring from the inferior surface, with the usual scoop-like lamellæ at the base. The tentacular cirrus is about one fourth the length of the palpus. A filiform process arises on the inner side below the peduncle of the tentacular cirrus, and extends some distance beyond it. There are also several elongated papillæ, one of which extends beyond the peduncle. From the basal part below the latter a series of very fine bristles pass forward—very minute traces of spines being present along the edge of the majority, while others, at the outer border of the tufts, show more evident spikes. The bristles form two tufts; and there is a spine between them. All the tentacular processes of the head are quite smooth.

The first foot has a very short superior lobe, with about a dozen long papillæ and the usual bristles. The inferior division is also short, with many papillæ and the pecu-

liar tapering bristles. The ventral cirrus is large, but does not quite reach the tip of the fleshy part of the foot. After the divisions of the feet become more distinctly marked, one of the papillæ in each becomes larger, that on the inferior lobe especially showing cellular loculi; posteriorly the papillæ are not thus differentiated. The superior fascicle has many whorled bristles with large spines, as well as the more finely serrated kinds. All the bristles of the inferior lobe have the canaliculated terminal process, tapering to a fine point (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 9). There is a semilunar process on the superior border of the foot; but no cilia are present. The branchial process begins about the sixth or seventh segment, and soon increases in size, reaching the tip of the foot about the twentieth segment. Certain whitish specks (parasitic?) appear in many of the branchiæ, and also in the skin of the ventral surface. The ventral cirrus has a process like a diverticulum at its base anteriorly; but such is not noticeable posteriorly. The scales are perfectly smooth round the margin, minutely granular under the microscope, and are tinged with light-brownish pigment. In small specimens curious nucleated anastomosing nerve-fibres are very conspicuous.

I doubtfully refer this form to the *Leanira yhleni*, Malmgren, who, unfortunately, says nothing more than that the scales are smooth, and that there are four eyes—two larger directed forward at the base of the antennæ, and two smaller superiorly in the middle of the head, the other parts resembling those of *L. tetragona*.

PSAMMOLYCE HERMINLÆ, Aud. & Ed.¹ Dredged in 35 fathoms in Tangier Bay, and more abundantly in Station 50, in 7-51 fathoms off the Algerine coast, on a bottom of mud and muddy sand, in 1870.

A large and boldly marked form, though all the specimens are incomplete. The largest reaches $1\frac{1}{2}$ inch in length, and is about $\frac{4}{10}$ inch broad. The dorsum is barred anteriorly with brown or black bands from the scales, then assumes a uniform dark brown or blackish brown, the scales especially being black with a lighter margin from the cilia. The under surface is pale or mottled in front for a short distance, then blackish or brownish. The bristles form a pale margin dorsally and ventrally.

The head is entirely concealed by the first pair of scales; and on their removal it is still overlapped by two large fleshy processes bearing their surfaces of attachment, and having a prominent papilla between them. The head, indeed, which extends behind these fleshy processes, is small and somewhat ovoid, with the anterior part produced into the enlarged base of the tentacle. A comparatively small eye is situated at the anterior border a little exterior to the base of the tentacle on each side, and another, somewhat larger, quite in the front of the head and below the former, so that it is scarcely visible from the dorsum. The tentacle arises by a broad and somewhat lozenge-shaped base, which gradually contracts into a prismatic process that reaches as far as the tip of the peduncles of the tentacular cirri. At this point the rounded filiform tip commences;

¹ If this should prove to be a new form, the name *P. carpenteri* may appropriately be given to it.

and it extends rather beyond the bristles of the region. The basal process of the tentacle rests on the large peduncles of the tentacular cirri, each of which has its termination (superiorly) rounded, and bears a tuft of bristles above, and the tentacular cirrus at its inferior surface, on a special peduncle. The bristles of this group are supported by a spine (which has its point near the inferior margin of the special peduncle just mentioned), and are for the most part stouter, especially in the neighbourhood of the tentacular cirrus, than those of the next series. A considerable portion of the shaft is bare, the distal end having whorls of distinctly separated spines, which, from the stoutness of the bristles, have a different appearance from the same parts in the succeeding forms, and which appear to typify the jointed kind of the next segment. A dense tuft of very fine bristles springs from a projection near the base of the peduncle; and beneath is another tentacular process, about a third shorter than the foregoing. The bristles have very slender tapering shafts with long whorled spikes. The palpi are fully twice the length of the tentacle, arise immediately below the peduncles of the tentacular cirri, are shorter than in *Leanira*, and quite smooth. At the inner edge of the base of each is a short curved lamella.

The first pair of scales are distinguished from all the others by their colour, shape, and coverings, and they form a sort of prow to the anterior part of the animal; they are irregularly rounded, with two prominent frills separated by a deep groove in front. The anterior margin of each frill is prolonged in the form of an ear-shaped process, the inner being the longer; the latter projects forward and inward, so as to guard the tentacular processes and bristles of the head, and, with its fellow of the opposite side, to constitute the prow formerly mentioned. The other process is directed slightly outward. The scale has a dense coating of grains of sand, which causes it to be of a lighter hue than any of the succeeding organs. This scale therefore agrees with what M. Claparède says of that of *Lepidopleurus inclusus*, viz. in being quite different from the succeeding scales; while the first pair in his *Psammolyce* scarcely differ from the others. Nearly the whole of its margin is covered with a close series of short papillæ—strongest on the posterior and outer margin, but largest on the internal border. They are short on the internal ear-shaped process in front, longer on the outer. The tips of the papillæ are somewhat blunt, and in the shorter ones occasionally globular, as at the posterior border. To modifications of cutaneous processes the fragments of gravel and sand are attached, the stalks being frequently wrinkled transversely, and generally of greater diameter than the ordinary granular papillæ. The second scale is irregularly reniform, the larger portion being external and the hilum in front; the anterior margin is smooth from the outer angle to the inner and anterior edge of the hilum. On the inner convexity of the scale some papillæ exist, few and somewhat short at first, then longer and more filiform at the inner margin of the scale. The latter has rather short granular papillæ as in the first scale (inner border), intermingled with more slender and much longer forms; the posterior border is furnished with both kinds, and also has very

short papillæ with globular heads, the distal margin being generally truncated. At the anterior and outer angle of the scale a few very short and somewhat globular papillæ occur on the anterior edge. The outer border, again, is occupied by a series of eminences, from each of which springs a series of long papillæ (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 10, the figure showing the first four papillæ), the short clavate warts of the anterior border being also continued in the intermediate space and over the surface. The first eminence (to the left in the figure) occupies the anterior angle, and has four long papillæ; the others follow, to the number of nine or ten, the last merging into the ordinary ciliated posterior border. The eminences vary in size; and the papillæ thereon range from one to ten in number. Moreover the latter are considerably larger than the ordinary papillæ on the scale; and a process (nerve or vessel) passes from the scale into the centre of each. The dorsal surface of the scale has many dark grains; and minute specks also occur on the cilia. The third scale has its anterior and outer angle more produced, thus extending the outer border, which has thirteen or fourteen eminences with papillæ, each increasing in size from before backward, though solitary papillæ occur between the eminences after the twelfth, thus by degrees linking them to the ciliated posterior border.

The scales gradually become shorter and rounder (though still reniform), and the cilia longer; while the eminences on the external border are fewer though more prominent, and with a larger number of papillæ. In some specimens eight or ten of the anterior scales are quite pale, covered with ordinary sand-particles, so that they are very rough, the last, however, becoming gradually darker. The first three pairs meet in the middle line of the dorsum; the rest are widely separated. The anterior portion of the dorsum is smooth; but by-and-by the surface is rendered rough by sand-particles, which, again, are frequently coated with black pigment. The under surface of the body varies in like manner—in pale specimens of a sandy hue, in dark specimens blackish. It is smooth in front, but thereafter covered with minute papillæ, which in the dark specimens are black. A parasitic *Loxosoma* occurs on the scales.

The first foot (which is directed forward) bears dorsally two dense tufts of long delicate hairs with an intermediate spine, each bristle being furnished with whorls of long spikes. Ventrally is a series of stronger bristles with long tapering shafts, having whorls of spikes and a slender smooth terminal piece tapering to a fine point (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 11, one of the superior ventral bristles). Towards the ventral edge of the foot the bristles become much more slender, and, instead of having most of the shaft covered with whorls of spikes, there are only ten or twelve at the distal end: a progressive decrease in this respect, indeed, occurs from above downward. The bristles have the same long needle-like terminal process. Just below the exit of the spine a long clavate process of the foot, like a short cirrus, occurs. The ventral cirrus is long and subulate, with a peduncle at its base. Both divisions of the foot are short; and the superior is furnished with a thin and broadly lanceolate lamella on its upper border, so that the lobe has a bifid appear-

ance. The second foot shows the leaf-like lobe superiorly, and a similar tuft of delicate bristles (stoutest inferiorly) with long spines. The inferior division has superiorly three or four rather stout bristles, with the distal end of the shaft enlarged and furnished with alternate rows of spines. The terminal process is comparatively small and bifid (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 12). Near the spine is a group of stronger bristles, the upper with, and the lower (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 13) without the spines on the shaft (the terminal process is bifid, and also comparatively small); then follow some slender forms with eight or ten spinous rows near the end of the shaft, and slender bifid tips (Pl. LXXIII. fig. 14), and others more slender than the first series, with spinous rows on the tip of the shaft; lastly, the dense inferior tuft with slender shafts spinous at the distal end, and long tapering terminal processes minutely bifid. There are a few minute bifid papillæ on the superior and inferior edges of the lower lobe, and a tuft of long filiform papillæ (often loaded with blackish pigment) below the spine. The ventral cirrus is of considerable size, long and tapering; it extends nearly to the tip of the bristles. There are some small papillæ on its basal process. The third foot shows a diminution in the length of the inferior bristles and their processes, and an increase in their strength. One of the upper bristles of the inferior ventral (long-tipped) series is represented in Pl. LXXIII. fig. 15, the bifid tip being scarcely noticeable. The dorsal bristles are likewise shorter; and their arrangement is interesting; for they spread all round in a fan-shaped manner, passing on the posterior aspect between the feet, so that the tips appear on the ventral surface. The leaf-shaped lobe is in front, and is the main cause of their disposal outward and backward. As we proceed posteriorly (*e. g.* in the region of the tenth foot) the strength of the ventral bristles increases, their number decreases, and their terminal processes become shorter. The filiform papillæ are also more numerous. The ventral cirrus presents a slight enlargement (in spirit) at its base, and the tip is somewhat dilated. The dorsal tuft of bristles is similar to the others, forming a kind of funnel open inferiorly, where the ventral lobe of the foot completes it, the tip of the superior lobe occurring in the pit of the funnel. One of the bristles from the upper part of the ventral series is represented in Pl. LXXIII. fig. 16.

This form appears to diverge from every species hitherto mentioned; but, owing to the want of precision in the published descriptions and figures, there is reason for doubt. In *Psammolyce arenosa*, Delle Chiaje, the four eyes are so closely arranged that they appear as a single pair, and the pinnate processes on the scales cannot be confounded with the tufted eminences of the present form; M. Claparède, moreover, describes the bristles of the first foot as of one kind. The *Psammolyce herminia*, Aud. & Ed., as originally described by the authors, and subsequently by M. de Quatrefages, has not been furnished with eyes; but they notice that the scales have their external and posterior margin "valde fimbriata et cristata," or, as in the original account, supplied with "petites crêtes membraneuses:" it shows very close resemblances. With such indefinite materials for forming a judgment, I have decided to place the species under

the name of Audouin and M. Edwards: those having the original and other closely allied forms will easily discriminate. It is distinguished from Claparède's *Lepidopleurus* by the fact, amongst others, that the latter has no eyes, and every foot is supplied with scales, whereas in this the scales are chiefly alternate. No other species of *Psammolyce* seems to approach it.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PLATES.

PLATE LXXI.

- Fig. 1. Portion of branchial process of *Euphrosyne lanceolata*, n. s. Magnified 350 diameters.
- Fig. 2. One of the radiating brittle dorsal bristles of *Chloëia fucata*, De Quatrefages? Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 3. Upper ventral bristle of the same species. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 4. Lower ventral bristle. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 5. Dorsal bristle of *Eunoa hispanica*, n. s. Magn. 90 diam.
- Fig. 6. Tip of the same. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 7. Ventral bristle of the same species (intermediate form). Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 8. Edge of a scale of *Lagisca jeffreysi*, n. s. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 9. Dorsal bristle of the same. Magn. 90 diam.
- Fig. 10. The same bristle. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 11. One of the longer (not longest) ventral bristles. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 12. Tip of another ventral bristle, showing secondary process. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 13. One of the stronger dorsal bristles of *Evarne johnstoni*, n. s. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 14. Tip of a dorsal bristle. Magn. 700 diam.
- Fig. 15. Superior ventral bristle. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 16. A bristle from the middle of the ventral group. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 17. Tip of one of the superior ventral bristles. Magn. 700 diam.
- Fig. 18. Tip of a bristle from the middle of the ventral series. Magn. 700 diam.

PLATE LXXII.

- Fig. 1. A nearly straight dorsal bristle of *Antinoë finmarchica*, Mgrn. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 2. A stouter slightly curved bristle from the same group. Magn. 210 diam.

- Fig. 3. Ventral bristle of *Antinoë mollis*, M. Sars, from the middle of the foot. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 4. The same. Magn. 700 diam.
- Fig. 5. Dorsal bristle of *Phyllantinoë mollis*, n. s. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 6. Ventral bristle of the same. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 7. Superior (ventral) bristle of *Lepidasthenia blainvillii*, Aud. & Ed. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 8. One of the inferior series. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 9. Superior (ventral) bristle of *Lepidasthenia longissima*, Blainville. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 10. One of the lower series. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 11. Bristle from the ventral edge of foot. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 12. Superior bristle of *Eupanthalis kinbergi*. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 13. Strong bristle of the same form. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 14. Bristle from the ventral edge of the foot. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 15. One of the same, seen in profile. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 16. Edge of a scale of *Sthenelais atlantica*, n. s. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 17. Superior ventral bristle of the same. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 18. Papillæ on the edge of a scale of *Sthenelais jeffreysi*, n. s. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 19. Papillæ of the corresponding scale of *Sthenelais boa*, Johnst., from St. Andrews. Magn. 350 diam.

PLATE LXXIII.

- Fig. 1. Superior ventral bristle of *Sthenelais jeffreysi*. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 2. Bristle from the inferior lobule of the same species, showing two divisions in the terminal process. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 3. Bristle from the ventral edge of the group. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 4. Superior ventral bristle of *Eusthenelais hibernica*, n. s. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 5. One of the slender group of bristles at the ventral border of the foot. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 6. Dorsal bristle of *Leanira hystericis*, Ehlers. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 7. Ventral bristle (anterior) of the same. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 8. Ventral bristle from the posterior region. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 9. Bristle of the ventral lobe of *Leanira yhleni*, Mgrn.? Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 10. Group of eminences bearing papillæ, from the outer edge of the second scale of *Psammolyce herminia*, Aud. & Ed.? Magn. 90 diam.

- Fig. 11. Superior ventral bristle of the first foot of the same. Magn. 90 diam.
- Fig. 12. Superior ventral bristle of the second foot. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 13. Smooth bristle near the spine in the same foot. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 14. One of the inferior group of the ventral division of the same foot. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 15. Superior ventral bristle from the third foot of the same specimen. Magn. 90 diam.
- Fig. 16. One of the upper ventral bristles from the tenth foot of the same example. Magn. 350 diam.
- Fig. 17. Dorsal bristle of *Lagisca jeffreysi*, with a pointed tip. Magn. 210 diam.
- Fig. 18. Dorsal bristle from near the body-line of the same form, with filiform or developing tip. Magn. 350 diam.

W.C.M. & G.R.F. del.

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